

OPINION

Reflections on United Nations' Decade of Action for Cryospheric Sciences and International Year of Glaciers' Preservation

Sérgio Henrique Faria ¹

1 Basque Centre for Climate Change (BC3), Leioa, Spain, **2** IKERBASQUE, Basque Foundation for Science, Bilbao, Spain, **3** Faculty of Science and Technology, University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Leioa, Spain

* sh.faria@bc3research.org

1. Why the cryosphere

Decades ago, when climate change was still called “global warming” and a younger Donald Trump was known as the quiff dude in goofy cameos, attempts to raise climate-change awareness were already in place. They would often involve some image of a beaten polar bear balancing on a floating chunk of ice, or grandpa’s old photos of a mighty glacier snout that gradually gave way to a silty moon-like landscape. Such early uses of natural ice as the canary in the coal mine highlight the pivotal role played early on by the cryosphere to announce the shape of things to come.

It is not just a matter of ice being sensitive to warm temperatures. The situation is more complicated than that. First, it also has to do with some complex climate phenomena, like ice–albedo feedback, polar amplification, elevation-dependent warming, and glacier response time [1] (see [Box 1](#)). Melting glaciers and ice sheets have been the largest contributors to global mean sea-level rise over the last two decades [2]. In particular, Antarctica and Greenland store so much frozen water to potentially rise sea levels globally by over 65 meters [3]. While a complete disintegration of these ice giants is unlikely to happen in the near future, these figures make it clear that even fractional changes in the mass balance of ice sheets can lead to massive discharges of fresh water, severely affecting sea levels and thermohaline currents, and possibly even triggering *tipping points* (i.e., abrupt and/or irreversible changes) [2]. Lastly, natural ice provides the most precise and reliable continuous records of more than 800,000 years of Earth’s climate history [4], which with new studies may soon surpass the million-year mark.

Beyond its climatic importance, the cryosphere is also crucial for life: glaciers are vital sources of water, not only for a wide variety of ecosystems, but also for three billion people worldwide [5]. For this reason, glaciers are often affectionately dubbed “the water towers of our planet.” This fondness for glaciers is widespread and deep-rooted in human culture, going far beyond the mere appreciation of an ecosystem service. For millennia, diverse cultures around the world have developed intimate social relations with their glaciers, regarding them as living organisms, often even sentient members of the community.

OPEN ACCESS

Citation: Faria SH, Arrizabalaga-Iriarte J, Cortés D, González-Santacruz N, Muñoz-Marzagon P (2025) Reflections on United Nations’ Decade of Action for Cryospheric Sciences and International Year of Glaciers’ Preservation. *PLOS Clim* 4(7): e0000674. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pclm.0000674>

Editor: Jamie Males, PLOS Climate, UNITED KINGDOM OF GREAT BRITAIN AND NORTHERN IRELAND

Published: July 23, 2025

Copyright: © 2025 Faria et al. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Funding: The authors acknowledge support by the State Research Agency of Spain (AEI) through PID2022-140975NB-I00 (MicroFAME) awarded to SHF, and also through MDM-415 2017-0714, MDM-2017-0714-21-1/PRE2021-096869 (DARKEX) awarded to SHF and DC, and CEX2021-001201-M awarded to BC3, funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033

awarded to BC3. Further support by the Basque Government grant PRE-2023-1-0131 (METAFIG) is also acknowledged awarded to SHF and JAI. This work has received Horizon Europe funding under the ICELINK grant agreement N° 101184621 awarded to SHF. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure, and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Competing interests: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Box 1. Some cryosphere-related climate phenomena [15].

Elevation-dependent warming: An enhancement (less commonly an inhibition) of warming within or above a certain elevation range. Characteristic of many mountain regions, it can lead to pronounced climate and environmental contrasts and changes within small areas.

Glacier response time: The delay of a glacier or ice sheet to adjust its volume and geometry to a new steady state, after climate has changed. It implies that a receding glacier is likely to continue its trend for decades after warming stops and the local temperature is stabilized. In the case of ice sheets, this delay reaches many centuries.

Ice–albedo feedback: Clean snow and ice surfaces are bright, with an albedo much higher (ca. 80%) than the average planetary albedo (approx. 30%). A warming climate melts the snow and ice cover, exposing low-albedo surfaces (e.g., ground, ocean). As a result, Earth’s albedo is reduced and more solar radiation is absorbed, accelerating warming. The same process, on a smaller scale, occurs when snow and ice surfaces are darkened by dust, black carbon, or other particles.

Polar amplification: The observed phenomenon that surface warming at polar regions significantly exceeds (up to several fold) the global average surface temperature change.

For instance, in Yukon and Alaska there is the traditional belief that cooking grease or fat meat near glaciers is an offensive hubris that may be punished with deadly glacier surges or outburst floods [6]. The glaciers’ sentience is so subtle that even a disrespectful attitude towards venerable beings or the glaciers themselves may provoke similar catastrophic retaliations. On the other hand, in the Karakoram, the Balti people developed over centuries the practice of grafting new glaciers on strategically selected sites, by laying together blocks of “male” and “female” ice from gendered glaciers, together with carefully selected twigs, straw and cloth [7]. After many years of snow accumulation, these young glaciers evolve into natural reservoirs of frozen water to alleviate periods of drought.

Despite industrial and technological revolutions, the truth is that the notion of glaciers as sentient beings has never completely vanished from our worldview. Climate change has recently unearthed these concealed insights, for instance through the recent practice of reaching remote locations to mourn the death of glaciers, holding glacier funerals, and erecting memorials commemorating the loss of our icy companions [8,9]. Today, science is re-evaluating the intricately multidimensional relationships between human and nature, rediscovering the importance of the local and traditional knowledge of sentient glaciers for sustainable water management and glacier preservation [10].

For all those reasons, it comes as no surprise that the United Nations General Assembly has declared the period from 2025 to 2034 as the *Decade of Action for Cryospheric Sciences*, with 2025 designated the *International Year of Glaciers' Preservation*, and with 21 March marked annually as *World Glaciers Day*. For 2025, various global and national events are planned (<https://www.un-glaciers.org>). These initiatives aim to raise awareness about the vital role of glaciers, snow, and ice for Earth's climate and environment, highlighting impacts on sea-level rise, the water cycle, and related economic and societal effects. Above all, they serve as urgent calls for collective action, inciting world leaders to reflect upon the climate crisis and the threat of a decaying cryosphere.

2. Prospects

Decades ago, when extreme events fuelled by atmospheric CO₂ concentrations above 400 ppm belonged to science fiction, Carl Sagan [11] wrote: “*Our civilization runs by burning the remains of humble creatures that inhabited the Earth hundreds of millions of years before the first humans came on the scene. Like some ghastly cannibal cult, we subsist on the dead bodies of our ancestors and distant relatives.*” Today, with atmospheric CO₂ concentrations ramping up beyond 420 ppm and on the way to smash 450 ppm by 2035, damaging extreme events are becoming commonplace, like a chronic planetary disease, and planetary tipping points are becoming dangerously less unlikely. And yet, alas, the “ghastly cannibal cult” persists, no longer subsisting only on “dead bodies”, but also on the livings and lives of the most vulnerable.

Dying glaciers are emblematic reminders that climate change is, before all, a *moral issue* [12]. We shall not slight their swan song. Many glaciers may vanish by 2034, but others will continue to nourish and marvel us: they deserve preservation. Today, the major challenges facing glacier preservation cannot be resolved solely by expert authority. They require the collaboration of various actors, both scientific and non-scientific, through transdisciplinary approaches merged with various forms of knowledge [13], by recognizing—as reminded by Karl Popper [14]—“*how little we know, and how much that little is due to people who have worked in many fields at the same time.*”

Let us make this Decade of Action for Cryospheric Sciences worthwhile. Coordinated collective action is the key. We do know what to do. Our world leaders do know what to do. What is holding back action is not lack of knowledge. It is lack of unfeigned willingness.

Author contributions

Conceptualization: Sérgio Henrique Faria, Jon Arrizabalaga-Iriarte, Daniel Cortés, Nicolás González-Santacruz, Patricia Muñoz-Marzagon.

Formal analysis: Sérgio Henrique Faria.

Funding acquisition: Sérgio Henrique Faria.

Investigation: Sérgio Henrique Faria, Jon Arrizabalaga-Iriarte, Daniel Cortés, Nicolás González-Santacruz, Patricia Muñoz-Marzagon.

Methodology: Sérgio Henrique Faria.

Project administration: Sérgio Henrique Faria.

Resources: Sérgio Henrique Faria.

Supervision: Sérgio Henrique Faria.

Validation: Sérgio Henrique Faria.

Visualization: Sérgio Henrique Faria.

Writing – original draft: Sérgio Henrique Faria.

Writing – review & editing: Sérgio Henrique Faria, Jon Arrizabalaga-Iriarte, Daniel Cortés, Nicolás González-Santacruz, Patricia Muñoz-Marzagon.

References

1. Faria SH, Carrascal DR, Ruiz L. Regional fact sheet – Mountains. In: Masson-Delmotte V, Zhai P, Pirani A, Connors SL, Péan C, Berger S. Climate change 2021: the physical science basis. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. 2021. Available from: <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/resources/factsheets>
2. Fox-Kemper B, Hewitt HT, Xiao C, Aðalgeirsdóttir G, Drijfhout SS, Edwards TL, et al. Ocean, cryosphere and sea level change. In: Masson-Delmotte V, Zhai P, Pirani A, Connors SL, Péan C, Berger S, et al. editors. Climate change 2021: the physical science basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press; 2021. pp. 1211–1362. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009157896.011>
3. Vaughan DG, Comiso JC, Allison I, Carrasco J, Kaser G, Kwok R. Observations: cryosphere. In: Stocker TF, Qin D, Plattner G-K, Tignor M, Allen SK, Boschung J. Climate change 2013: the physical science basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. 2013.
4. Jouzel J, Masson-Delmotte V, Cattani O, Dreyfus G, Falourd S, Hoffmann G, et al. Orbital and millennial Antarctic climate variability over the past 800,000 years. *Science*. 2007;317(5839):793–6. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1141038> PMID: [17615306](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/17615306/)
5. United Nations. The United Nations world water development report 2025 – mountains and glaciers: water towers. Paris: UNESCO. 2025.
6. Cruikshank J. Do glaciers listen? Local knowledge, colonial encounters, and social imagination. Vancouver: UBC Press. 2005.
7. Tveiten IN. Glacier growing - a local response to water scarcity in Baltistan and Gilgit, Pakistan. MSc Thesis. Ås, Norway: Department of International Environment and Development Studies, Norwegian University of Life Science (UMB). 2007.
8. Schmidt JJ. Glacial deaths, geologic extinction. *Environmental Humanities*. 2021;13(2):281–300. <https://doi.org/10.1215/22011919-9320156>
9. Varnajot A, Salim E. The hauntology of climate change: glacier retreat and dark tourism. *Tourism Geographies*. 2024;27(1):102–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616688.2024.2328607>
10. Moulton H, Carey M, Huggel C, Mutschmann A. Narratives of ice loss: New approaches to shrinking glaciers and climate change adaptation. *Geoforum*. 2021;125:47–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2021.06.011>
11. Sagan C. Billions and billions: thoughts on life and death at the brink of the millennium. London: Headline. 1997.
12. Jamieson D. Managing the future: public policy, scientific uncertainty, and global warming. In: Scherer D. Upstream/downstream: essays in environmental ethics. Philadelphia: Temple University Press. 1990;67–89.
13. Brugnach M, Sato-Bajracharya S, Kranz L, Bilbao-Barrenetxea N, Faria SH. A multidimensional approach to knowledge coproduction in glaciology. *J Glaciol*. 2024;70(e35): 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jog.2024.74>
14. Popper KR. The myth of the framework: in defence of science and rationality. London: Routledge. 1994.
15. IPCC. Annex VII: glossary. In: Masson-Delmotte V, Zhai P, Pirani A, Connors SL, Péan C, Berger S. Climate change 2021: the physical science basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change; 2021. Cambridge University Press. 2021;2215–56. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009157896.022>